

RESULTS OF AN EMPIRICAL STUDY OF PERSONAL PSYCHOLOGICAL DEFENSE IN EXTREME SITUATIONS

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Abstract. *In this article, the level of awareness of the situation and the adequacy of behavior in the event of an unexpected life danger are largely determined by the innate characteristics of a person, his attitude, type of nervous system and a number of other psychobiological indicators. how to train and be ready.*

Key words: *emergency situation, extreme situation, extreme conditions, protection, reaction, mental changes, impact, voluntary action, resource, resistance.*

РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ ЭМПИРИЧЕСКОГО ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ ЗАЩИТЫ ЛИЧНОСТИ В ЭКСТРЕМАЛЬНЫХ СИТУАЦИЯХ

Аннотация. *В данной статье уровень осознания ситуации и адекватность поведения при возникновении неожиданной жизненной опасности во многом определяются врожденными особенностями человека, его мироощущением, типом нервной системы и рядом других психобиологических показателей. как тренироваться и быть готовым.*

Ключевые слова: *чрезвычайная ситуация, экстремальная ситуация, экстремальные условия, защита, реакция, психические изменения, воздействие, произвольное действие, ресурс, сопротивление.*

Discussions about the problems of “psychological defense mechanisms” and coping behavior” in extreme situations arose a long time ago and continue to this day. This means that there are practical and theoretical difficulties in identifying defense mechanisms and coping thresholds. Often these processes manifest themselves purposefully. Also, the behavior of psychological defense occurs in external situations and performs the function of “resolving internal conflict” and participates as a mediator in the conflict between consciousness and the unconscious. In extreme situations, psychological defense reflects: denial, repression, rationalization, depression, identification, catharsis and many other forms.

Defense mechanisms work effectively due to their powerful criteria for stopping anxiety and overcoming fear. According to S. Freud, “human existence is characterized by the struggle with fears and anxieties that arise in various situations.” Each of the components of extreme living conditions has positive and negative consequences depending on its significance and subjective assessment by a person. At the same time, a person is characterized by a situational understanding of these components of extreme states, on the basis of which both personal (positive) changes and pathological changes in behavior can occur. When exposed to extreme stimuli, the mental processes and states of a person change (perception, perception, thinking, memory, emotions, etc.).

Possible pathological disorders may be depression, phobia, anxiety disorder. Extreme episodes change the value system (what was previously insignificant becomes important and valuable), but obsessions, manias, etc. may appear. Extreme situations help change the target behavior, but conflict, aggression and irritability are possible. The environment changes a person’s

mental organization for the better (empathy, communication, help, etc.), but depression, psychopathic deviations, and psychological trauma can develop. The environmental factor contributes to changes in the spiritual organization of a person (search for meaning, development of will, courage, heroism), however, the lack of spirituality can lead to the loss of moral principles. Mental protection can be divided into three types according to its functional function and complexity according to age stages. They consist of:

1) sensory-psychological protection – protection occurs in the body through psychosensory control of behavior.

2) perceptual psychological protection - as a result of the use of perceptual psychological control, the individual develops protection.

3) psychological protection of the individual - protection arises in a person as a result of a person's behavior, activity and conscious actions.

Perceptual and sensory protection in humans are associated with the biological needs of a person (to continue to exist while maintaining individuality). Its goal is to preserve and protect conflicts during the psychological development of personality in a person and interpersonal relationships.

In these conflicts, a person participates not as an organism or a person, but as an individual. Thanks to pre-formed habitual strategies and the relative immutability of behavior in extreme situations, a person always reacts through a system of interpersonal relationships (asks for help, manipulates, shows aggression, helps others, etc.). It is as if he is involved in some kind of interpersonal game, the exit from which can be very difficult. For example, a victim game in which the roles are predetermined: Victim, Aggressor, Rescuer. Such relationships are built on the basis of a person's unhealthy reaction to the intrusion of an extreme event and often traumatize the individual. Thus, the assessment of an event in the conditions of a certain social system, the attitude towards it is influenced by cultural and historical conditions, specific characteristics of the situation (emergency, extreme), as well as the level of formation of a certain social system struggle. Strategies that allow you to talk about a person's individual history (biography). Nowadays, extreme conditions are woven into a person's biography, more permanent than situations, and it is important that they contribute to the development of a person's readiness or unpreparedness for extreme influences. In a person's psychological readiness for extreme influences O.S. Shiryayeva, S.V. Kondrashenkova, Yu.A. Surikova identifies five components:

1) a positive assessment of the limb, including its assessment as a challenge;

2) non-normative activity as a creative direction for processing traumatic experience, an active life position, etc.;

3) orientation towards mutual assistance as a focus on cooperation, altruism versus selfishness;

4) the strength of the "I", which means high neuropsychic stability, willingness to take risks, responsibility, independence;

5) the desire for subjective richness of life, variety and intensity of impressions as an assessment of the completeness and quality of life.

These resources increase a person's adaptive abilities, regardless of the nature of the extremes. Thus, from a psychological point of view, we can talk about two layers of personality development in extreme conditions:

1. contribute to the development, growth and development of a person under the influence of extreme stimuli, episodes, relationships, situations, environment;
2.) victimization, turning a person into a victim of extreme stimuli, episodes, relationships, situations, extreme environments.

When using all these components, a person may find himself in very difficult life situations. However, these conditions can become an impetus for him not only to pathological changes and sacrifice, but also to the possibility of transformation and positive high intrapersonal changes. Any pathological personality changes are often considered extreme cases. They are based on mental illness, dysfunction of the body, which becomes the main criterion for an extreme state. D.G. Tagdisi and Ya.D. Mamedov (1991) describe the body's reactions to extreme stimuli in the form of the dynamics of the development of extreme states: mobilization, resistance (stability, resistance), overexertion, fatigue (a type of unconditional inhibition, which in brain cells, corresponding cortical structures there is an excessive increase in the strength, duration or frequency of excitation) and fatigue again.

If at first extreme states represent adaptive reactions of the body, then (due to duration, extreme intensity, transcendence) they can be pathological in nature. The main pathological reactions of a person to extreme situations, their duration and the consequences of their experience are presented in the textbook "Psychology of Stress". It should be noted that today the human condition is considered in several aspects: it is an indicator of the dynamics of individual and holistic human reactions, caused by internal and external factors. Therefore, a person's reaction to extreme situations is closely related to his circumstances. In fact, the manifestation of an extreme situation associated with various factors has a direct negative impact on the psychological nature of a person. As a result, a person experiences a certain level of depression. To get out of this depressive state, it is necessary to provide a person with psychological help. To do this, first of all, it is necessary to know the psycho-emotional factors that cause an extreme situation. These factors include:

1. Manifestation of various emotional actions that cause dangerous situations.
2. Lack of necessary information at the moment and lack of information aimed at mitigating the situation.
3. Excessive mental, physical and emotional stress.
4. Adverse weather effects: extremely hot temperature, extremely cold temperature, lack of oxygen in the air, etc.
5. Famine, drought, etc.

It should also be noted that in extreme situations, the human body more often falls into a state of stress. To provide psychological services to people, it is very important to know the essence and causes of stress. Therefore, Hans Seele (1907-1982), Nobel Prize winner, is an outstanding physiologist. According to the scientist, patients under stress are more likely to experience loss of appetite, decreased mobility, increased blood pressure and depression. G. Seele defines these

symptoms of stress as “a sign of a simple illness.” Locus of control determines how effectively a person controls the environment and influences its changes.

There are external (external) and internal (internal) control centers. External people perceive events as random and as the influence of external forces beyond human control. Introverts believe that almost all events are within the sphere of human influence. In their opinion, even catastrophic situations can be prevented by thoughtful human actions. They spend their energy obtaining information that will allow them to influence the course of events and develop specific plans of action. Internal organs know how to control themselves and successfully overcome extreme situations.

Psychological stability (endurance) shows how strongly a person can withstand the effects of stressful and extreme situations. It includes a number of factors, including locus of control, personal self-esteem, level of criticality, optimism, and the presence or absence of internal conflicts. The best psychological resilience is also achieved by beliefs and moral values that allow you to give personal meaning to an extreme situation. Personality is formed under the influence of the social environment. Therefore, the indicator of human safety or risk taking is not only an innate quality, but also the result of development. Inadequate formation of a person's individual characteristics manifests itself in extreme cases (and such cases usually precede and accompany accidents). A person's propensity to take risks significantly increases emotional balance, the inability to quickly divide attention and highlight the main object among a large number of other objects, insufficient endurance and excessive (too large or too small) appetite for risk.

Psychological analysis and research is one of the most subtle and unique arts, requiring deep knowledge and skill. If you connect personality to psychological study in an extreme situation, then the branches of psychology will expand and turn it into one of the necessary areas. At the same time, sensitivity in extreme situations and their types (such as panic, fear, escape), the dynamics of an extreme situation and the uniqueness of this situation are also fully studied, and psychological help can be provided to a person in such a situation. situation.

At this time, in the era of developed civilization, we can often encounter extreme situations. In such a situation, a person must first of all find help from himself. This help is psychological help. In case of fear, anxiety, crying, convulsions, confusion, feelings of guilt, the ability to control physical movements, nervous tremors, anger, rage, aggression and stressful situations, the formation of psychological abilities, skills and knowledge in a person is used to ensure that the situation is positive, they bully.

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